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Tracing Oppression and Marginality through Humanimal Tensions in Ivan Turgenev's *Mumu* and Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay's *Mahesh*

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Abstract:

The short stories *Mumu* and *Mahesh* deal with a unique humanimal relationship. They narrate the relationship between an oppressed human and a helpless animal. The protagonist in the *Mumu*, Gerasim is deaf and mute serf who has befriended and adopted a dog. A weak, malnourished working bull has been with Gafur and Amina for many years in the story *Mahesh*. Although concepts of marginality and oppression seem blurred in the two short stories, they are intricately rooted in the dynamics of power structure. The paper aims to showcase the treatment of animals in domestic and cultural spheres as a reflection of societal attitudes towards humanimals. In both stories, the protagonists Gerasim and Gafur are victims of Tsarist serfdom in Russia and socio-economic rifts in rural Bengal, respectively. Even though geographically distinctly located the stories are eloquent debates for understanding Judith Bulter's notions of "normativity," that explains certain lives are socially grief worthy and others are disposable. This paper proposes for ethical consideration of humanimal relationship, which for Kenneth Shapiro is "kinesthetic empathy."

Keywords: Oppression, Marginality, Normativity, Kinesthetic empathy, Humanimal.

Introduction

Short stories have the power to present impactful and insightful perspectives in limited space. The chosen literary texts are known for their brevity and concise narrative. *Mumu* a short story by Russian writer Ivan Turgenev published in 1854 makes powerful attempts to succinctly critique the issues of serfdom and authoritarian power in nineteenth century Russia. The opening lines of the story offer a glimpse into the feudal society and the lonesome Landlord.

“In one of the outlying streets of Moscow, in a gray house with white columns and a balcony, wrapped all askew, there was once living a lady, a widow, surrounded by a numerous household of serfs. Her sons were in the government service at Petersburg; her daughters were married; she went out very little, and in solitude lived through the last years of miserly and dreary old age...” (Turgenev 1)

The mistress of the house is a capricious, impulsive and short-tempered woman. Under this mistress works an agile and able serf named Gerasim who was deaf and mute. He had strength equal to four men and was punctual to pay his seigniorial dues. He was a dutiful serf who accidentally rescues a pup by the riverside and nurses it to life. “No mother could have looked after her baby as Gerasim looked after his little nursling...” For Marjorie Garber, animals often bring out the best in human beings. (Garber 15) Erica Fudge furthers this idea only to explain how living with an animal, forces human beings to rethink humane, humanity, and humanness. (Fudge 3) Like many animal studies scholars argue it is impossible to understand human history without looking into role and status of animals. Fudge quotes Cary Wolfe, who opined that “we

disavow the animal in order to constitute ourselves.” Thus, human being does not exist in isolation and the presence of an animal adds value to the human and vice versa.

Anastassiya Andrianova analyses disability as primarily “a metaphor, a textual device and a deficit that made Gerasim’s muteness the kernel of social allegory and his deafness, the vehicle to generate pathos for the hearing audience.” To critique the dehumanising effects of serfdom, Turgenev uses Gerasim’s physical strength as a contrast to his socially powerless condition. His inability to speak is allegoric of the voiceless serfs controlled by the nobility. Serfdom is a system in which a landowner can monitor the lives and deaths of her servants and animals alike. Gerasim’s characterisation echoes comparisons to real animals on the one hand and an animal-like giant or beastly on the other. (Andrianova 55) Beastly is rhetorical in fairy tales and folklores, say Shakespearean slave Caliban, from the play *Tempest*, is a befitting example of such a portrayal. The ideology that operates tries to reinforce the notion of an enslaved person under colonial subjugation. It indirectly addresses serfdom as brutish, coarse and devoid of filial relations. Just like Oscar Wilde’s *Selfish Giant* Gerasim in Turgenev’s *Mumu*, is a “dumb giant.” Gerasim finds refuge in his dog, Mumu and they both develop mutual love, trust, loyalty and dependency that is what Marjorie Garber meant when she said “dog love is love.”

In an authoritarian world, “all animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others,” is a popular statement from George Orwell’s *Animal Farm*. Oppression involves unjust treatment of individuals or groups of individuals, often through denial of agency. The farm animals toiled for the pigs, and the pigs live in comfort and luxury. Likewise, the system does not allow deviation from servitude. The nameless mistress in the story *Mumu* represents the absolute authority which is often self-serving and arbitrary. For Judith Butler, power subtly operates

through norms, institutions and language. The mistress considers Mumu as a subject that will immediately submit to her deaf master.

“The old lady began to call the dog in a coaxing voice. She stooped down and was about to stroke her, but Mumu turned her head abruptly, and showed her teeth. The lady hurriedly drew back her hand... ” (Turgenev 20)

This incident becomes a life changing instance for Gerasim and Mumu. The mistress dictates her servants to get rid of the dog not based on any serious accusations, but on personal discomfort. For Fudge “pets provide ontological security,” and Mumu gave Gerasim a sense of stability. This humanimal bond figuratively broke the boundaries of distinction between Gerasim and Mumu. Andrianova “identifies the two through their shared logocentric exclusion from the human community,” this anthropocentric attitude for her enables, the mistress to decide whose life is socially disposable. Power for Michael Foucault operates through institutions and knowledge systems that deal with the human and the animal. The dogs in the animal clinic that David Lurie volunteers to euthanise are victims of the same disposability in J M Coetzee's *Disgrace*. Serfdom does not legally dictate that a serf to be loyal or to live a life of total submission, but that is how most serfs have been living, and now it has become a norm. In a condition where serfs are not allowed to express their feelings or desires, Gerasim's unique affinity with the dog, is a deviance from the so called-norm. Such deviant trait and unacceptable behaviour is nipped in the bud, hence, the mistress instructs immediate disposal of the voiceless dog. Turgenev demonstrates the Landlady's agitation in the following conversation with Gavril, another servant.

“It's simply introducing disorder. There's no one in control in the house- that's what it is. And what does the dumb man want with a dog? Who gave him leave to keep dogs in my yard?

Yesterday I went to the window, and there it was lying in the flower garden; it had dragged in some nastiness it was gnawing, and my roses are planted there... Let her be gone from today... do you hear?"(Turgenev 21)

Wendy Woodward, in her article, seeks to redefine the lives of dogs in *Triomf* by Marlene Van Niekerk and *Disgrace* by J M Coetzee. She attempts to bring out an interesting connection between meat consumption and Lucy's rape. (Character from *Disgrace*) For Woodward, "the helplessness of the animal killed for consumption is same as Lucy's inability to voice the injustice in racist South Africa." The violence against women and animals is a pursuit that upholds virile culture. (Woodward 96) Similarly, such arguments are traced in Justyna Wlodarczyk's *Geneology of Obedience*,

"The fate of slaves' hunting dogs in the late 1850s was supposed to serve as a reminder of the status of slaves themselves: they were chattel to be disposed of freely by their masters." (Wlodarczyk 72)

Bringing in the Foucault's biopolitics, Justyna tries to justify why dogs owned by slaves were easy victims of white atrocities. She states, "white slave owners could not target the slaves directly because slave labour was key to Whites' economic prosperity and killing canine bodies was indirectly hitting slaves emotionally." In the study of subaltern, Gayatri Chakrabarti Spivak calls such an act as "epistemic violence." The act of excluding, silencing or misrepresenting the ways of knowing and understanding the world is a form of epistemic violence. (Spivak 271) Gerasim, though isolated by his condition, knows the dog went missing after the mistress' instructions. The tragic end of *Mumu* says little about the killing and speaks volumes about the absence of justice and empathy in an authoritative hierarchical society.

Normative according to Butler legitimises violence and gets portrayed as natural and never contingent. In *Gender Trouble*, she reviews how gender roles get imitated and normalised and how any act of defiance is suppressed. The passivity of other serfs in *Mumu* helps maintain rigid power structure and perpetuate oppression. The realities foregrounding serfs imprisoned in a system by arbitrary authority allow systemic violence to persist. The ones trapped in the corrupt system can be complicit in enforcing oppression. Other servants who pulsate with Gerasim are unable to convince the mistress to allow him to have the dog. Through their passive presence, Turgenev highlights how power, supremacy and authority are sustained through generations of disciplining. In Butlerian notion, norms create identities and compel conformation to the hierarchy. Stepen and Gavrilla attempt to shelter Gerasim and Mumu, but they are unable to retaliate. They are agency-less puppets in the hands of the mistress. Power permeates through social appropriation and such a condition is eloquently narrated when Antoinette's dog Toby is set ablaze in Jamaican writer Jean Rhys *Wide Sargasso Sea*. The death of Toby during the terrible fire at Coulibri Estate is symbolic of Antoinette's loss of innocence, a sense of security and colonial tensions. (Rhys 17) Toby is symbolic of vulnerability because it is a helpless dog and it is in the hands of the wrong owner.

Cruelty for Arnold Arluke is expressed differently in different situations. He calls people as authors of cruelty, because the definition of cruelty has influenced by the person exercising it. He asserts that when people indulge in cruelty against animals, such stories get refashioned positively. (Arluke 7) Violence and cruelty has reshaped to suit the cultural practices, religious duties and law. In the same light one can consider *Mahesh* by Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay as an apathetic text that covertly presents humanimal suffering. The story focuses on a drought-hit village somewhere in rural Bengal. The zamindar or landlord of the village had good command

over his subjects and the people too regarded with awe. In this Hindu majority village lived a poor peasant named Gafoor, with his daughter Amina and Mahesh, a working bull. Gafoor was deeply in knee deep in debt due to crop failure and a shortage of rain. His precarious agrarian livelihood is similar to Gerasim's serfdom. Though geographically and chronologically apart the chosen stories highlight the protagonists Gafoor and Gerasim to be victims of oppression, exploitation, and marginalization. Justyna uses the expression, "Whites have treated aborigines like dogs-" to critique the conditions of aborigines equal to a dog that was chained, shot, poisoned or euthanised. (Włodarczyk 73) This explains Gafoor and Gerasim's helplessness as they face multifaceted alienation and discrimination. Gafoor has been doubly oppressed as a poor Muslim man living in a Hindu village. The villagers refuse to sympathise with Gafoor's inability to provide for Mahesh, and this ignorance decides Mahesh's tragic end. Animal cruelty has been redesigned to suit the needs of the hegemonic structure, thereby proving Arluke's hypothesis on cruelty.

The 1918 short story *Mahesh* is a scathing critique of how the socio-economic conditions of the owner is imperative on the pet animal. Susan McHugh takes lessons from George Orwell's *Animal Farm* and discovers that "deconstructive literary theory has worked to elaborate the operations of animality at the heart of identity or human subjectivity." That meant reading about animals as metaphors, and making animals mere "figures for and of humans." (McHugh 24) This anthropocentric reading has been challenged in the two chosen stories. Mahesh, the bull, is essential for Gafoor to till the land but is now weak due to poverty, hunger and starvation. The weak bull overshadows Gafoor's vulnerability. It humanises animal suffering and prepares readers to sympathise with Gafoor rather than Mahesh.

Erica Fudge in *Pets* discusses the role of communication between the owner and his pet, she highlights that communication in humanimal is through routines, gestures, body language and emotional connect. She writes, “we learn to read our pets, and they learn to read us.” Through reading, she is suggesting mutual understanding, care, love, and affection that develop over a period of time once one shares their life with an animal. Consequently, Gafoor tries to protect the animal from anything seemingly inappropriate condition and this unvocal communication is a testimony to what Donna Haraway emphasizes by “mutuality.” For Haraway, mutuality finds its place in co-definition; she rethinks the concept of agility training not as an act of dominion but instead as a conversation. The word F-E-T-C-H is a conversation both the partners (pet dog-human) have learned to communicate, with an ultimate aim to cohabit. The probable misbehaviour of Mahesh is anticipated in Gafoor's interaction with Tarkaratna, which is illustrative of Haraway's “inter-reliance of companion species.” (Fudge 109)

“‘When I passed this way in the morning he was tethered there,’ said Tarkaratan, and now on my way back he's still tethered the same way. Karta will bury you alive if you kill a bull. He's devout Brahmin.’ ...‘Where can I turn him loose, Baba Thakur? The winnowing isn't done, the grain is still lying in the fields. The hay hasn't been sorted, the earth is burning, there's not a blade of grass anywhere. What if he eats someone's grains or hay — how can I turn him loose, Baba Thakur.’” (Chattopadhyay 19)

The intricacies that enmesh the socio-cultural milieu of pre-independent India has been poignantly presented in this short story. The harsh reality of peasantry in a severe drought-hit region of Bengal is a microcosmic representation of the conditions of peasant pan India. Analogous to this condition is the 2001 film *Lagaan* by Ashutosh Gowariker, that uses entertainment to present the conditions of drought stricken rural India and opprobrium of

taxation under colonial rule. The exploitative taxation policy leaves Gafoor with no hay for the famished and ravenous Mahesh, the working bull on whom he is dependent for food and livelihood. The dilapidated roof of the hut, empty utensils and Gafoor's ill-health are indicators of his poverty-stricken lifestyle. Due to starvation Mahesh is weak and his ribs can be counted. The zamindars who were intermediaries to collect taxes for the colonisers, helped drain wealth of the country. The repeated ill-treatment, abusive language and rituals of deference redirect the reader's attention to Judith Butler's concept of 'performativity.' The roles of zamindars and peasants are sustained and constructed through constant internalised subordination and performance of hierarchies. Gafoor's socio-cultural marginalisation can be seen as a double-edged sword, oppressing him as a poor Muslim peasant that in a precarious agrarian community. Susan McHugh observes in *Wuthering Heights*, Isabella's springer spaniel dog is indicative of problems for and with the wealthy class. She writes, "the dog shares particular advantages and hazards of sharing identity with the owner." (McHugh 88) Resembling the deaths Toby, Mumu and many other animals whose sacrifice to traumatised their owners and Mahesh too was no exception. The animal was starving and the Brahminical class that worshipped bovine as sacred and holy left no stone unturned to get rid of the bull, simply because it was in the hands of a wrong owner.

Twentieth century India was deeply influenced by western capitalism and industrialisation. Mahesh had taken ill and had become unfit for work, economically non-productive and hence disposable. After Mahesh had destroyed Manik Ghosh's garden, an elderly man offered to buy the ailing bull for ten rupees. In the end when Mahesh is beaten to death and two cobblers take his body slinging on a pole took him to the dumping ground, their shining knives makes Gafoor tremble. The systemic indictment of commodifying animal body reflects how humanimal bodies

are valued only for their utility. Gafoor's actions are a result of frustration, desperation and pent-up emotions. The economic duress, nonintervention of any institutional aid and unsympathetic neighbourhood, shatters Gafoor significantly. All the human characters in the short story ignore the fact that Mahesh is a sentient being with the power of autonomous action. Marx and Engels for Tim Ingold viewed "the animals, as raw material of human projects." Domestication made animals, objects in socio-economic organization, which he regards as a necessary criterion for the 'social appropriation of nature' by human subjects. Also, domestication of animals is a cultural activity that includes use of force for controlling and taming of animals. Animals in pastoral communities are objects for authority and domination. Ingold calls this 'a dangerous attitude,' that can affect humanimal lives alike.

Intersectionality is a concept that has its roots in Black Feminist movement in America. The same concept has been used to describe the ambivalence prevalent in the study of humanimal relations. It was argued by the Black feminists that the mainstream theories promoted inequality. They believed women's experiences have been compartmentalised into class, gender, race, but in real world these ideas are intersecting or overlapping. Similarly, oppression and marginality of the humanimal in the short stories chosen for analysis have social systems and power structures interlocking. The analysis is incomplete if one considers gender, race, class alone, one must explore species identity as a criteria. People of colour, lower class, disability, and limited means have all been animalised. This way Cary Wrenn, a sociologist places animalisation as the foundation of oppression. She believes intersectionality is "recognising animalisation at the foundation of all human systems of inequality." It is on this basis that any identity formation takes place. (Animals & Society: Episode 4)

Identity for Animal Rights activist Peter Singer is an important spiciest activity. Peter Singer coined the term, Speciesism, to discuss preference for one species over another. Animals have been used for food, research, and entertainment and humans ignore the interests of animals because they belong to another species. This ignorance for the humanist school of thought was purely because animals lack rational, autonomy and self-awareness. This prejudice is crux for posthumanist thinkers like Derrida who believed human being consciously ascribes irrationality to animals, to identify itself as unique and superior. The sustenance of anthropocentric ideas have been seen in the climax in both short stories. The pain endured by Mumu and Mahesh has little to do with the animal. It undoubtedly causes distress for their owners, but their death is evident of decayed, outlawed and anarchist societies. If on the one hand these animals are creative literary device that evokes emotional outrage and insensibility, then on the other hand it also raises questions of ethics and humanity. The stories animalise the human counterparts, Gerasim and Gafoor, within their respective social structures.

Conclusion

Butler's concepts of normativity and performativity resonates the chosen texts. The texts showcase that oppression and marginality are normalised by the people in power to maintain the hegemonic control and identity. These identities are performed and repeated through generations of conditioning. Finally, the chosen texts call for 'kinesthetic empathy,' which according to Kenneth Shapiro is the ability to feel or understand the bodily and emotional state of another being or through another being's bodily experiences. (Shapiro 184) Say, Mumu innocently drinking the last bowl of soup and Mahesh lapping water from the bucket are instance that makes the readers pulsate pain, sorrow, and helplessness of Gerasim and Gafoor. Therefore, the death of these animals has been read as shared bodily experiences of sorrow and suffering.

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